

Research Software Engineers as Maintainers: Keeping Code Alive

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Abstract

In recent years, scientific research groups, especially at universities, have desired the expertise of the human equivalent of a Swiss Army knife for software: the research software engineer (RSE). RSEs are known by many job titles, like *data scientist* and *research support staff*, and likewise have a plethora of duties from writing software for HPCs to building models to visualizing results in plots. As RSEs prominence rises, a wave of software sustainability efforts has blossomed, centering software as an increasingly vital component in research. At the same time, funders of software and infrastructure projects stress reusable components to streamline development efforts across institutions. In addition, the shift from closed systems to ones using open source software components has led to the question: How can we view RSEs over time? In this position paper, I argue that RSEs should be viewed as maintainers of software. Software cannot be sustainable or reusable without a maintainer performing the work. In university spaces where graduate students come and go, and PIs are focused on research results, RSEs emerge as key through lines of continuity in long-term projects, fonts of historical knowledge, and navigators of the increasingly thorny scientific software stacks.

In recent years, scientific research groups, especially at universities, have desired the expertise of the human equivalent of a Swiss Army knife for software: the research software engineer (RSE). RSEs are known by many job titles, like *data scientist* and *research support staff*, and likewise have a plethora of duties from writing software for HPCs to building models to visualizing results in plots. RSEs might be undervalued, and uncredited for their toils or worse, pejoratively thought of as data janitors [1]. Ideally, RSEs are valued members of their teams, whose work is credited, cited, and lauded as part and parcel of the project. As RSEs prominence rises, a wave of software sustainability efforts have blossomed, centering software as an increasingly vital component in research [2]. New funding calls highlight that software matters, such as the recent Ford-Sloan Critical Digital Infrastructures funding opportunity and the new NSF calls for cyberinfrastructure projects [3]. Funding calls for reusable components of digital infrastructure further cement the idea of sustainable computing systems that not only function collaboratively across institutions, but last over time as well.

As research about the centrality of software in scientific research increases over time, efforts to solve the sustainability challenges continue, asking questions about documentation, storage, citation, and other topics related to keeping code alive, that is, usable and understandable [4]. To this end, I argue that software cannot be sustainable without a defined, associated human performing the work. In university spaces where graduate students come and go, and PIs are focused on research results and not software, I ask: Can we view the RSE as a maintainer of software?

In Silicon Valley, the mantra ‘Move fast and break things’ seems diametrically opposed to what RSEs do: they work on code for projects that span years if not decades, code that depends on critical principles of metrology; code that must perform calculations in specific, precise manners. Code that might yield different results, like machine learning algorithms in non-deterministic computing. This is one core tenet of the difference between science and non-scientific software projects, the additional layer of ‘theory-software translation’, that is, the challenges to represent scientific theory within, and to be represented by, code and data [5]. RSEs must carefully and methodically write code that does both functionally and theoretically correct analysis in a transparent way, and increasingly, with an eye towards reproducibility. Silicon Valley software fads and trends are viewed skeptically, new languages or libraries need to be vetted and researched before they are trusted and introduced into systems. Dependencies must be dealt with, as do containers and hardware and anything else that might affect the running and compiling of code. Historians Russell and Vinsel [6], [7] argue that maintenance activities far supersede those of innovation in terms of importance. The Sloan-funded Maintainers initiative, (www.themaintainers.org) recognizes “these crucial individuals who keep society’s systems running”. The group has recognized technological maintenance as a crucial aspect of their work.

I argue that there is potential for viewing RSEs not only as engineers but as maintainers, not only of software but of institutional memory, a through line essential for the understanding of software’s functionality over time. In this view, not only is software --but expertise-- sustained and valued. Documentation and metadata, no matter their breadth or depth, are no match for an experienced human in the moment explaining how something works.

RSEs as maintainers add not only a human but a historical dimension to software development; GitHub can only tell us so much about *who* did *what*, *when* with respect to code, and most importantly *why were changes implemented?* [8]. In the astronomy research group I work with now, even though there are decent documentation practices being exercised, I often find myself trying to figure out what this version is for, or why is that one branch is used. RSEs can often be in institutions for long periods of time, thus gaining the tacit knowledge that comes with experiencing code environments, domains, institutions, and the requisite people. I see RSEs as maintainers of software-- not in a way in that they are *responsible* for everything running smoothly, but in a holistic way, in that they possess the deepest understanding of the big picture: where code lives, who uses what, a layered map, if you will, of all the human and code processes that occur within their domain. In this way, the RSEs as maintainers are the

keepers of the code-knowledge, cementing their necessity as part of research groups and institutions.

Naturally, cons of such a position include the possibility that responsibility turns into accountability, where the RSE becomes liable for portions of the project outside of their control. This is unfortunately common in the realm of software-making, because of a lack of understanding of the work required to create and maintain code.

This position paper stems from a case study in astronomy, observing a research group utilizing a ground-based observatory in the United States. The group has lasted for twenty-five years, accompanied by a byzantine codebase comprising at least eight programming languages and innumerable versions and described using Hinsen's *scientific software stack* [9]. Like many research groups, each member has their own agenda plus make contributions to group work, resulting in a hydra-like assemblage of scripts to analyze astronomy data, making up two main pipelines of code. As postdocs and graduate students come and go over the years, the institutional memory keepers are the longest-serving members. These might include emeriti, PIs, and the research staff. The research staff who maintain the pipelines can certainly be considered RSEs, both working at their parent observatory or at the university. In my research, I found that pipeline maintenance work was inevitably time-consuming and, as invisible labor, was in constant tension with the need to produce novel software solutions for new instruments. Replacing outdated software was another task requiring a great deal of effort.

Prioritizing software in science centers the Research Software Engineer as an essential component. Maintenance work implies that RSEs should not just write code to solve a problem and move on, they are necessary to keep the science research going, hopefully leading to stable careers. This way of thinking requires scientists and institutions to understand the nature of scientific software development over time. PIs know RSEs are essential workers, but how so is not well articulated. I recommend a surfacing of maintenance work into the vernacular of reporting, of research, in funding, proposals and job descriptions as critical for better science. In a world where the discoveries and publications often come first, we should center RSEs as maintainers, as necessary to further scientific research.

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